

CLASSROOM CULTURE OF GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS: MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION WISE ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of the study is to compare classroom culture of government and private higher secondary students with regard to Tamil medium and English medium of instruction. The investigator used survey method of research for this study. The investigator has selected 150 government higher secondary students and 150 private higher secondary students from 5 government schools and 5 private schools respectively. For selected the students, the investigator used random sampling method. The tool used in the study is Classroom Culture Scale which is validated by the investigator (2018). The statistical technique used in the study is, t-test. The investigator found that there is significant difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect to English medium. The private higher secondary students perceive better classroom culture than government higher secondary students.

KEYWORDS : Classroom Culture, Higher Secondary Students, Tamil medium, English medium

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is so much more than creating lesson plans and delivering them to your students. The teaching environment is equally as important as what is being taught. Students will thrive in a space that they feel comfortable in, so if you're too focused on lesson plans, you may be missing a vital piece of the puzzle. A positive classroom culture is beneficial to the teacher and students as it creates a classroom where students feel part of something great. Classroom culture involves creating an environment where students feel safe and free to be involved. It's a space where everyone should feel accepted and included in everything. Students should be comfortable with sharing how they feel, and teachers should be willing to take it in to help improve learning. Having a classroom that is welcoming and safe is the foundation for better learning. If students do not feel like they belong, this can prove to be a major hindrance to their education. A positive classroom culture empowers students to be part of their own learning experience and to take responsibility. Creating a positive learning environment is essential for success in the classroom. Teachers should create a welcoming atmosphere where student feel safe and willing to share. Classrooms should be a place where students feel respected and feel their contributions matters. No student should be singled out or secluded in the classroom. Every student should feel accepted, wanted and respected.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Education improves the qualities of human behavior. Today we live in a competitive world where academic excellence is a must for success in life. One of the goals of higher secondary stage of education is to equip the school learners with the necessary knowledge and skill to participate as adults in social and economic life of the larger society. An atmosphere or environment that nurtures the motivation to learn can be cultivated in the home, in the classroom, or at broader level throughout an entire school. Much of the recent research on educational motivation has rightly centered on the classroom, where the majority of learning takes place and where students are most likely to acquire a strong motivation to gain. But achieving the goal of making the individual classroom a place that naturally motivates students to learn is much easier if students and teachers function in a school culture where academic success and the motivation to learn is expected, respected and rewarded. An atmosphere where students learn to love learning for learning's sake, especially insofar as it evolves into academic achievement, is a chief characteristic of an effective school. Classroom experiences may assist

children to think, reflect, reason and effectively utilize their understanding. Classroom contexts that engage students in dialogue, evaluate the quality of their own thinking and the thinking of others, provide opportunities for indepth and sustained probing, and require participants to try out ideas and rethink their own, attend to the heart of learning as understanding and inquiry. Classroom culture is seen as a major determiner of classroom behavior and learning, understanding how to establish and maintain a positive classroom culture is seen as basic to improving schools. With this background, the investigator want to compare classroom culture of government and private higher secondary students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out whether there is any significant difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect to Tamil medium.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect to English medium.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- There is no significant difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect to Tamil medium.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect to English medium.

METHODOLOGY USED

The investigator used survey method of research for this study. The investigator has selected 150 government higher secondary students and 150 private higher secondary students from 5 government schools and 5 private schools respectively. For selected the students, the investigator used random sampling method. The tool used in the study is Classroom Culture Scale which is validated by the investigator (2018). The statistical technique used in the study is, t-test.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect to Tamil medium.

Table-1

t-test showing the difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect to Tamil medium

Variable	Tamil Medium	N	M	SD	t-Value	Table Value	Remarks
Classroom Culture	Government	118	1.4721	19.76350	0.399	1.962	NS
	Private	93	1.4616	18.36898			

It is inferred from the table that the calculated t-value (0.399) is less than the table value (1.962) for (209) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It indicates that there is no significant difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect to Tamil medium.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect English medium.

Table-2

t-test showing the difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect to English medium

Variable	English Medium	N	M	SD	t-Value	Table Value	Remarks
Classroom Culture	Government	32	1.4559	13.89096	5.365	1.990	S
	Private	57	1.2847	15.38797			

It is inferred from the table that the calculated t-value (5.365) is greater than the table value (1.962) for (209) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is significant difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect to English medium. The government higher secondary students perceive better classroom culture than government higher secondary students.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

The investigator found that there is no significant difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect to Tamil medium. But there is significant difference between government and private higher secondary students in their classroom culture with respect to English medium. The private higher secondary students perceive better classroom culture than government higher secondary students. So the management of private schools allow their teachers to build and maintain positive relationships with students for the development of good classroom culture.

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